

Innovative Methods of Teaching and Learning

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Abstract

Education, being a social institution serving the needs of society, is indispensable for society to survive and thrive. It should be not only comprehensive, sustainable, and superb, but must continuously evolve to meet the challenges of the fast-changing and unpredictable globalized world. This evolution must be systemic, consistent, and scalable; therefore, school teachers, college professors, administrators, researchers, and policy makers are expected to innovate the theory and practice of teaching and learning, as well as all other aspects of this complex organization to ensure quality preparation of all students to life and work. The objective of this paper is to incorporate Innovative methods and technology in teaching and learning to create a rich learning experience for students and a rewarding teaching experience for faculty.

Keywords: Innovative teaching and learning, Education Technology, Implementation, problem-based learning. Environmental approach to teaching, pedagogy

Introduction

Advance pedagogy is the way to enhance teaching and learning performance. Different innovative teaching methods are now in use across the globe. Hybrid teaching includes e - learning in addition to the face to face teaching. Use of technology and multimedia is described in details. Use of smart gadgets for different tasks like teaching, designing question papers, assessment of student, feedback and research methodology is discussed. The application of

innovative teaching and learning methods is critical if we are to motivate and engender a spirit of learning as well as enthusiasm on the part of students. The role of education is to ensure that while academic staffs do teach, what is taught should also be intelligible to students emanating from culturally and linguistically diverse backgrounds and that they rapidly become familiar with the expected standards. It is more often than not the case that students underachieve because of the fact that they have not grasped an awareness of the level of assessment or what it is that the lecturer expects from them. Lecturers should thus apply themselves to utilizing innovative methods so that the students' learning process is as free-flowing as possible and that the methodology they adopt is conducive to learning. Innovative teaching and learning methodologies such as short lecture, simulation, role playing, portfolio development and problem-based learning (PBL) are very useful in addressing the rapid technological advances and developing workplaces that will be required in the foreseeable future. Teaching with technology engages students with different kinds of stimuli involve in activity based learning. Technology makes material more interesting. It makes students and teachers more media literate. Technology is a means to justify the end of composition outcomes and has become a seamless extension of the curriculum in the classroom. Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge captures the qualities of this new hybrid educator who must find his or her place between the intersections of these qualities. To most effectively teach technology, we must model that technology within our disciplines and classes.

The biggest challenge any teacher faces is capturing the students' attention, and putting across ideas in such a way that it stays with them long after they have left the classroom. For this to happen, classroom experience should be redefined and innovative ideas that make teaching learning methods more effective should be implemented. So here are some innovative ideas that will help teachers reinvent their teaching methods and make their classes interesting. The use of innovative methods in educational institutions has the potential not only to improve education, but also to empower people, strengthen governance and galvanize the effort to achieve the human development goal for the country. The purpose of this paper is to suggest useful innovative teaching methods which could easily be imparted knowledge to the students.

Methods of Innovative teaching

1. Learning through Argumentation

Students can advance their understanding of science and mathematics by arguing in ways similar to professional scientists and mathematicians. Argumentation helps students attend to contrasting ideas, which can deepen their learning. It makes technical reasoning public, for all to learn. It also allows students to refine ideas with others, so they learn how scientists work together to establish or refute claims. Teachers can spark meaningful discussion in classrooms by encouraging students to ask open-ended questions, restate remarks in more scientific language, and develop and use models to construct explanations. When students argue in scientific ways, they learn how to take turns, listen actively, and 4 Innovating Pedagogy 2015 respond constructively to others. Professional development can help teachers to learn these strategies and overcome challenges, such as how to share their intellectual expertise with students appropriately.

2. Incidental Learning

Incidental learning is unplanned or unintentional learning. It may occur while carrying out an activity that is seemingly unrelated to what is learned. Early research on this topic dealt with how people learn in their daily routines at their workplaces. For many people, mobile devices have been integrated into their daily lives, providing many opportunities for technology-supported incidental learning. Unlike formal education, incidental learning is not led by a teacher, nor does it follow a structured curriculum, or result in formal certification. However, it may trigger self-reflection and this could be used to encourage learners to reconceived what could otherwise be isolated learning fragments as part of more coherent and longer term learning journeys.

3. Team Teaching, Cooperative or collaborative learning process

When teacher and students have to work under so many constraints, then the practice of “Team teaching or cooperative or collaborative teaching” is always a good option. Team teaching or cooperative learning process is a team work where members support and rely on each other to achieve an agreed-upon goal. Cooperative learning is a successful teaching strategy in which small teams, each with students of different levels of ability, use a variety of learning activities to improve their understanding of a subject. Each member of a team is responsible not only for learning what is taught but also for helping teammates learn, thus creating an atmosphere of

achievement. Students work through the assignment until all group members successfully understand and complete it.

4. Design Thinking

This technique is based on resolving real-life cases through group analysis, brainstorming, innovation and creative ideas. Although “Design Thinking” is a structured method, in practice it can be quite messy as some cases may have no possible solution. However, the Case Method prepares students for the real world and arouses their curiosity, analytical skills and creativity. This technique is often used in MBA or M.Tech classes to analyze real cases experienced by companies in the past.

5. Blended-Learning and Teacher Education

Blended learning describes an approach to learning where teachers use technology, usually in the form of Web-Based instruction, in concert with and as a supplement to live instruction, or perhaps utilize components of a learner-centered Web course with components that require significant instructor presence and guidance. The strength of a blended-learning approach is that it provides a means to ensure learners are supported and guided as they undertake independent learning tasks. Use of the Web in such settings provides many affordances for the teacher and students in the form of communication channels, information sources and management tools. These aspects appear to make blended-learning particularly well suited to teacher training students, especially those in large groups where direct instructor support may be difficult to deliver. Blended-learning commonly describes learning that combines traditional teaching and learning approaches with information and communication technologies. It is anticipated that blended learning will enhance the student learning experience, at the same time it also demands that the teachers should be trained as online facilitator.

6. Voice Threads to Build Student Engagement

Voice Thread is a web service that allows users to upload PowerPoint slides, videos, photos, *et al.* and add voice narration to create a multimedia presentation. Voice Thread is an application that runs inside your web browser and it allows you to transform collections of media, like images, videos, documents, and presentations, into a place for a conversation. These conversations are not live, but take place whenever it's convenient for the people to participate. They are also secure, with simple controls that let you dictate who can participate and what they can do. Educators use Voice Thread for many different reasons, from extending and

documenting classroom conversations, online tutoring, virtual class spaces, professional development training, and a thousand things in between. The advantages of the voice thread are as follows. It starts student driven discussions with better understanding. It is a great way to deliver projects and solicit feedback.

7. Teaching- Learning Websites, blogs, Apps and

Massive open online courses

There are many websites and apps which provide information relative to a particular course or many courses. Teachers can also create their own website or blog and share their knowledge. Not only teaching, assessments can also be conducted online. The learners can also post their doubts or questions related to any subject, which can be answered by any of the person having knowledge about it. Liberty in sharing of knowledge enable learners to work on any subject. In addition to classroom courses, they can take any course online, this enhances the scope of getting jobs in multiple fields. Learners can gain knowledge and apply it in doing complex projects which need knowledge of more than one field. National Program on Enhanced Learning is one such website which is widely used all over India. It contains the course content in the form of both notes and video lectures. Learners can take lectures free of cost and enhance their knowledge. **Swayam** digital is another example of online learning. It is global public platform for both teachers and learners. Any faculty can create his/her course and upload it and interested learners can take the course. Many such platforms exists like Coursera, **IIT BombayX** and **edX** which gives various courses.

8.Prezi–Your Presentations

Prezi is a new way to do the presentations. Prezi is a versatile app that lets you make professional-looking presentations. It's like a free, pared-down version of PowerPoint. Prezi lets you make presentations that are as casual or as professional as you want them to be. It allows you to add information to a prezi organize it in a logical way, embellish it with audio and video and then share it with the people you need to reach. Prezi makes making a presentation very easy. The whole app flows very easily even without looking at the intro or help; you can dive into a new presentation fairly competently. It is worth looking at the help and online resources to get the most out of it, but even taking Prezi in isolation, it's very usable. Before Prezi, there was PowerPoint, and to a large extent, that was it. PowerPoint is a great piece of software, don't get us wrong, but there was definitely room for a change. Prezi feels fresh and easy, but still

produces nice looking presentations. It's also capable of dealing with feature rich and complex material and making it look good.

9.Social Bookmarking

Bookmarking is the simple process of saving the address of a website in the favorite folder of your web browser so that you can find it again later. Social bookmarking takes these process two steps further. Firstly, instead of saving the bookmarks to your favorite folder, it saves them online. The great advantage of this is that you can then access them from any computer, not just the one you saved them on, simply by logging into your social bookmarking account. This enables you to access your favorite sites from wherever you are, rather than wherever you bookmarked the site. The second advantage is the social part. Saving bookmarks online enables you to easily share them with other internet users and for you to access their bookmarks as well. This can help you find and access many more useful websites; especially as many social Book marking sites enable you to join special interest groups and finds people who have similar interests to you. The benefits of social bookmarking are that it is easy to share and manage social bookmarks. Searching and storing in database is also easy.

10. Podcast in Classroom

Podcasts are serial recordings, posted regularly online. Basically, producing podcasts is the technology based equivalent of oral lectures. Lectures and news have been shared with listeners, who download the files online. The advantages of podcast are its flexibility, reusability of your lecture. It is advantage for the hearing impaired students.

11. Screencast

Screencasts have emerged as a prominent teaching tool on the Internet. Screencasts are an effective way to share ideas, deliver content, and obtain student feedback .Screencasts can be used for describing a step-by-step process, explaining a particular concept, or presenting a Power Point presentation with narration and multimedia elements. A screencast can be used in any class as a part of real time instruction or as the lesson itself as in the flipped teaching model. With the flipped teaching method, instructors use screencast videos to deliver their lectures, assigning them as homework. Then, in class, students can ask questions as they work through problems that they normally would have done at home without teacher help. Creating an educational screencast that meets content objectives requires a systematic approach to planning. It seems clear that screen casting is a powerful, highly effective, and affordable learning tool that can

facilitate learning across any curriculum area. Screen casting is a remarkable instructional tool. These are the free software's available for instructors which teach and saves time. Jing, Screen jelly, screen, Screencast are some of the freebies available.

12. Social media in to education

A social media where individuals are in communities share ideas and interests. Some popular communities are: Facebook, MySpace, YouTube, blogs, Twitter and delicious. Face book and other social media have been hailed as delivering the promise of new, socially engaged educational experiences for students in undergraduate, self directed, and other educational sectors. Concerns of social media Concerns: Loss of control, Time commitment, unnecessary information, Information overload anyone can create official account for your university

13.Smart Boards

Smart products bring learning to life, helping students experience a deeper level of engagement and understanding by making course content interactive and visual. The ease of use built in to each product enhances instructional efficiency. Instructors can begin delivering course material with the simple touch of a finger or a pen, save comments and notes made in digital ink, and distribute saved content directly to students. Smart products are flexible, complementary and evolving. This means the products you choose today will work together now and in the future as your technology requirements change.

14. Flipped Classroom

The Flipped Classroom Model basically involves encouraging students to prepare for the lesson before class. Thus, the class becomes a dynamic environment in which students elaborate on what they have already studied. Students prepare a topic at home so that the class the next day can be devoted to answering any questions they have about the topic. This allows students to go beyond their normal boundaries and explore their natural curiosity.

15. Moodle

It is Open source system to help design your session. Moodle is Virtual Learning Environment which provides staff and students with access to electronic teaching and learning materials such as lecture notes and links to useful websites and activities such as discussion forums, group it is something that lets you capture your experience, note, website and photos. Ever note is also a great tool for teachers and students to organize all of their own content. One can download the application. They can organize all of their notes and handouts in an Ever note notebook it is

portable, searchable, and indestructible. Even if you they lose their phone, their data is safe in the Cloud. In addition to systematizing notes for class, it's a great tool to use for research activities students can store images, PDFs, and even hand written notes.

Many Teaching Options

- Chat rooms
- Discussions board
- Webinars
- Emails
- Social media in class rooms
- Image creators

Conclusion

Any teaching method without destroying the objective could be considered as innovative methods of teaching. There searchers believe that the core objective of teaching is passing on the information or knowledge to the minds of the students. There are a number of ways that teachers can bypass the system and offer students the tools and experiences that spur an innovative mindset. Education is a light that shows the mankind the right direction to surge. The purpose of education is not just making a student literate but adds rationale thinking, knowledgeable and self-sufficiency. When there is a willingness to change, there is hope for progress in any field. Creativity can be developed and Innovative teaching and learning benefits both students and teachers.

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